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netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

First cycle Activity artefacts collection

WP6_D6.3

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1. INTRODUCTION

The focus of the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017) is on giving children and young people a clear voice for their concerns and interests in relation to the digital society. In contrast to traditional observation-based research, which can only tell us what people have been doing, the project's generative research approach allows us to gain deeper insights about their motivations, by giving participants free rein to their creativity in expressing their concerns, their attitudes and expectations through a variety of media and formats. This allows their voices to be heard in a variety of ways, and provides much deeper access to the potentials of children and young people that the WYRED project is trying to explore, and to make visible in such a way that it can inform policies. The groups' activities are generating a wide range of artefacts, such as videos, digital stories, publications, music, art, reports, images etc. The artefacts will be collected on the WYRED platform which, among other things, will be used as a repository of results and raw data generated by the research. These will be published on the WYRED platform, with artefacts freely accessible for public consumption¹.

The present work package focuses on the second phase of the WYRED cycle, where the consortium aims to facilitate a wide range of exploratory activities, called research activities, during which groups of children and young people, internationally or locally, investigate and examine the issues that concern them in the digital arena. They do this through creative projects (e.g. prototyping solutions following an ideation session to tackle pre-defined challenges) or more conventional research projects. As in the previous stage, interaction during the research activities will ideally take place on the platform, though some users may prefer other media. Each group working on an open research activity administers a dedicated space on the platform to record and review work progress.

As previously mentioned, the WYRED project is structured in cycles. During the first cycle, research activities for this work package (Phase 03) have been adjusted based on the the results of the evaluation work (Phase 04). As shown in the following infographic, the initial set of activities and project plan yielded some artefacts. The subsequent evaluation work allowed us to adjust the aim. Based on the Activity Toolkit and on didactical material created as a core deliverable for this work package, workshops with Young People and Children were run with specific goals in mind, systematically producing artefacts.

¹ <https://platform.wyredproject.eu>

Figure 1: 1st Cycle of the WYRED Project (WYRED Consortium, 2017)

Table 1: 1st cycle numbers of WP6

Quantitative Indicators	Target value	1st cycle value
Average number of active participants per country per cycle	30	280
Average number of research activities per country per cycle	5	5
Average number of research activities types per cycle	5	5
Number of artefacts generated per cycle	80	104

2. DELIVERABLE WP6.3: IMPLEMENTATION OF ACTIVITIES

Much of the work of deliverable 6.3. involves creative activities by young people in response to a particular question or issue. Since the different research groups involved in the project were meant to design their own processes, it was correctly anticipated that guidance would welcome and, to this end, a toolkit of generative research activities (templates and guidelines) was generate as a specific deliverable. The toolkit was distributed to all participants, and also made available on the WYRED platform (García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-

Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018). All partners made good use of the activity toolkit while facilitating research activities.

During the 1st Cycle of the project, the participants focused on designing and implementing research activities in order to explore the issues identified in the previous stage, using a range of approaches, with the support of the partners. Participants worked in groups to design and implement their own activities, with the facilitation of the partner organisations. Furthermore, groups were able to present their ongoing work as public projects in the common area in the WYRED platform, and in the respective community areas created for them by the partner organisations. Participants are able to read projects made public by the project owners, as well as comment on them and cast their vote. This allows Young People and Children to compare and contrast their experiences with projects run by peers across participating countries, covering a variety of topics in English and/or in local languages.

The screenshot displays the WYRED platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HOME, COMMUNITIES, PROJECTS, EVENTS, and HELP, along with a USER ACCOUNT dropdown. Below this is a banner for WYRED, 'The platform for the young', with a breadcrumb trail: HOME > PROJECTS > PUBLIC PROJECTS. The main heading is 'Public projects'. A yellow box prompts users to 'Please fill in the Inclusion Questionnaire before you go on.' Below this, it states 'Public projects: 82' and notes that private projects are only available within private communities. There is an 'Etiketler' (tags) search bar. A filter section includes 'Dil' (language) set to '- Herhangi -', 'Sıralama anahtarı' (sort by) set to 'Gönderi tarihi' (upload date), and 'Sıralama' (sort) set to 'Azalan' (decreasing), with 'Uygula' (apply) and 'Sifirle' (reset) buttons. Four project cards are visible:

- What's wrong with the education system:** Project by High School students from 'Hof HaSharon' regional high school in Israel. Group called 'Shfayim Community'.
- Vittime di bullismo: la storia di chi in sé ha trovato la luce:** Stories of bullies who find light. (Read more)
- I giovani e il mondo del lavoro:** 'Ciao a tutti! Mi chiamo Elisabetta Svalacchia e studio Scienze politiche per la Cooperazione e lo Sviluppo all' università degli Studi di Roma Tre.' (Read more)
- Giovani, identità e politica: una storia alternativa:** Project born from the need to understand the relationship between young people and politics. (Read more)

Figure 2: Public projects on the WYRED platform

The screenshot displays the WYRED platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HOME, COMMUNITIES, PROJECTS, EVENTS, HELP, and USER ACCOUNT. Below this is a header section with the WYRED logo and the tagline 'The platform for the young'. A breadcrumb trail shows the path: ANA SAYFA » COMMUNITIES » DOĞA COMMUNITY » PROJECT. The main title of the project is 'THE ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY ROOFS: TO OBTAIN ENERGY FROM RAIN WATER ON THE ROOFS SHAPED IN THE FORM OF M'. A yellow notification bar asks the user to fill in an inclusion questionnaire. The project description explains the use of renewable resources and the design of 'M' shaped roofs for rainwater collection. It includes tags for 'environment', language 'English', and a voting section. Below the description, there are two columns: 'Sonuçlar' (Results) with a PDF file named 'ROOFS.pdf' and 'Community' with instructions on how to join the 'Doğa Community' or the 'Welcome community'.

Figure 3: Community Area on the WYRED platform

3. RESEARCH TOPICS & RECOMMENDATIONS

Research topics and questions were identified through the Delphi and Social Dialogues, data was collected by stakeholders and participants. All partner organisations afterwards defined 4 research topics, for which a range of activities were then envisaged by participants, including drama, film, creative digital arts, digitally-mediated educational and other informal learning activities and other research projects. This stage generated quantitative data, narratives, artefacts and other outputs subject to interpretation in the following stage by the research participants themselves, the consortium and third parties. The aims to encourage participants, through reporting on their research activities, to generate “thick descriptions” of the processes involved (Geertz, 1973) were achieved overall. The outputs of the research activities are stored in the WYRED platform repository, exploiting data standards relating to generative research methods. Open Access criteria are applied, including about the exploitation of existing platforms².

Artefacts of different kinds, such as videos, sculptures, publications, music, reports, and images, produced during the participant research phase, will be initially stored in the group spaces, and then in the WYRED knowledge base. The artefacts collections will be delivered according to the two cycles implementation.

All partner organisations implemented different sessions and activities with the groups of children, YP and stakeholders to work on the research processes. Some groups have finalized their research and can provide already some conclusions and/or artefacts, while others are still in the process of completing their project.

All current 1st Cycle project work is listed on the following pages, independently of the status of completion, together with comments and recommendations from participants, if available. In total, 280 participants aged 8-23 contributed to 104 projects to date.

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/wyred?page=1&size=20>

4. LIST OF PROJECTS

Table 2: Universidad de Salamanca artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Alejandro Hernández Gómez, Sara Sánchez Herrera, María Sánchez Peix	Globalization, nation and individual in today's world	texts, drawings, physical book	texts, pictures and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-lucha-la-existencia	YP need to find their own identity and build their own values. They refuse to be tagged as selfish, materialistic, by adults who probably do practice these attitudes. YP do not resign themselves to adopting a conformist attitude and struggle to change the world in which they live
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Héctor Crego Alejandro, Diego Sánchez Román, Álvaro Vicente Sánchez	Globalization and education	draw my life animation	video and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/efecto-la-globalizaci%C3%B3n-educaci%C3%B3n	Even in a global world, education is still under control of governments, which in many cases deliberately manipulate people through education. It is crucial to develop open, free and critical educational systems to avoid manipulation
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Juandiego Huete Petisco, Carlos Fonseca García	Globalization, economy and education	draw my life animation	video and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/starbucks-rwanda-rift-valley	Globalization and media (specially smartphones) are changing our world in such a way as to compete with primary instances of socialization (family, school) and so having increasing importance
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Laura Arroyo Montero, Coral Riesco Viñuela,	Feminism, illegal immigratio	website website	website and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e	Feminism is a necessary and global movement in our time

	Carla Seco Hernández	n, society and tradition			individuo-mundo-actual/project/feminismo-inmigraci%C3%B3n-ilegal	
IES "Venancio Blanco"	María Fraile Alonso, Clara García Pérez, Ángela Garrote Pérez	Feminism	website website	website and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/ni-una-menos	Feminism is about past and present, but is above all future
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Ignacio Amador López, Pablo Diego Blas, Javier González Sánchez	A new Europe	Documentary film	video and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/una-nueva-europa	Education, initiative and exchange between nations are the principles that should guide the youth in building a new Europe.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Vera Rodríguez Corcho, Manuel Ruiz Villuendas, Guillermo Santos Rodríguez	The face of society	Short film	video and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/face-society	In a globalized society, consumerist and permanently attached to technology and mobile phones, young people have to find their place in the world, their own identity, unique and non-transferable, individual and intimate.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Selene Almaraz Sánchez, Paula del Rey Velasco, Borja Pantín Alonso	Influencers and the use of social networks	Short film	video and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/impacto-la-globalizaci%C3%B3n	Faced with the phenomenon of influencers and the use of social networks, especially in the construction of the individual identity of adolescents, the influence of the family context on the construction of the vocation and personal identity is valued.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Ana Guzmán Germán, Elena Prieto Villoria, Marina Sánchez Pedraz	Homophobia	Essay	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/homofobia	Through a history of homophobia, a reflection on the reasons why it continues to exist in our days is proposed, while pointing out the need to move towards the acceptance of sexual diversity.

IES "Venancio Blanco"	Daniel Martín González, Alberto Santos Hernando	Feminism	Social research report	documentary film and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/feminismo-%C2%BFcu%C3%A1nto-sabe-la-gente	How much do people know about feminism? It is a question for society in general, which young people have used to interview people of different ages on the street on issues related to feminism.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Sara Ayuso Patrocinio, Esther Redondo García, Angelina Suárez Quevedo	Past and present environmental problems	Collection of photos	photos, png documents and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-realidad-nuestra-naturaleza	We must be aware of the main environmental problems that affect our world, and that have affected us throughout history.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Carolina Cano Marcos, Marta Cenzual Salvador, Ana Segurado González	Discrimination against women, racism and classism	Research work	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-desigualdad-sus-distintos	Discrimination against women, racism and classism are the subject of research for young people who want to draw society's attention to three fundamental forms of inequality among human beings.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Cristina Cuesta Sánchez, Jimena Hernández Sánchez, Ana Rodríguez Criado	The evolution of the concept of society	Report	ppt presentation and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-sociedad	The evolution of the concept of society, the construction of identity and nationality, as well as the phenomenon of globalization are topics for discussion that young people want to share with policy makers in this project.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Carlos Sevillano García	Globalization, nation and individual in today's world	Report	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual	Globalization confronts us with positive and negative elements in the construction of the concept of identity and nation.

					<u>identidad</u>	
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Paula Catoya Zurdo, Natalia Pérez Alfaraz	Nation, personal identity and vision of a global world	Short stories	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/alumnas-inspiradas	Write short stories can be a way of narrating one's vision of nation, personal identity and vision of a global world.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Celia Cabezas Puerto, Natalia Martínez Renedo	Social networks in a globalized world	Short film	video and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/las-redes-sociales-un-mundo	The forms of communication have evolved. What are the criticisms that society makes about novelties?
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Nadia de la Nava Colmenero	Globalization, nation and individual	Essay	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/no-nos-olvidemos-la-realidad	There are different perspectives in the analysis of the concepts of globalization, nation and identity, such as the philosophical, social and economic point of view.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	María del Río Pérez, Lucía Cortés Hernández, Carlos Santos Bravo	Globalization, nation and individual in today's world	Prezi presentation	presentation and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/mundo-actual	There is space for personal and groups' reflections in the analysis of the actual world
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Iñaki Gómez Palenzuela, Francisco Iglesias Santos, Sergio	Understand our world	Short film	video and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-	Be aware of the difficulty of understanding the world around us.

	Martín Martín				actual/project/how-3	
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Jesús Martín Pérez, Darío Núñez Rodríguez	The effect of globalisation on our city	Report and collection of photos	pdf document, pictures and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/globalizaci%C3%B3n-desde-nuestra-ciudad	The effects of globalisation are around us, just look at your city.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Xuan Cai, Marta Hernández Cañas, Sandra Manzano González	The evolution of education	Research work	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/influencia-la-educaci%C3%B3n-nuestra-vida	It is important to know the evolution of education, to better understand our society.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	María García Cirilo, Paula García Iglesias, Sergio García Sánchez	Feminism	Report	ppt presentation and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/feminismo	It is necessary to reflect on feminism as an element of identity, as a national and global reality.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Luis Alponente Gendres, Óscar Barbero Hernández	Effects of globalisation on the environment	Report	ppt presentation and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/un-mar-pl%C3%A1sticos	We have to take measures to save the environment.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Pablo González Ávila, Sergio Hernández Matos	Ideologies and feelings in the YP lives	Short story	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-	We can be separated by ideologies but united by feelings.

					<u>actual/project/cuento</u>	
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Raffaela Bruzzone Torres, Pablo López Rebollo, Noelia del Pozo García	The importance of social networks	Podcast	podcast file and making-of	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/radio-sol	The importance of social networks told in a podcast.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Nerea Andrés Velasco, Raquel Cabrero Ledesma, Ana González Alfaraz	The phenomenon of nationalisms	Social research report	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/paseo-por-la-realidad	To know the phenomenon of nationalisms
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Ricardo Pastor Pérez, Julio Gaspar Pro Rodríguez, Juan Carlos Velasco Sánchez	Personal identity and bullying	Documentary film	video and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-vida-timmy	We must support young people in their struggle to identify their vocation and overcome the harassment of other colleagues.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Rodrigo Gómez Castro, Iván Navas García	“Local” stereotypes on globalization	Short story	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-globalizaci%C3%B3n-mundo	There are “local” stereotypes on globalization to be analyzed in a more comprehensive way.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Sergio López Alvarado, Víctor Sánchez Hernández	Origins of globalization and its current importance	Research work	pdf document and making-of video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-	Investigate the origins of globalization and its current importance to understand the current world.

					<u>globalizaci%C3%B3n-origen-y-actualidad</u>	
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Miguel Ángel Honrubia Barbero, Sergio Pérez Morocho, Francisco Álvaro Salort Sánchez	Yihadismo	Report	ppt presentation and making-of video	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/yihadismo</u>	Investigate religious fanaticism to understand the origin of recent violent acts.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Sergio de Antonio Samaniego, Lucía Monje Mesonero, Lucía Nieto Moreta	The relationship between people who live in a dystopian world	Letters	letters, pictures and making off	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/cartas-para-no-ser-le%C3%ADdas</u>	In a dystopian world, reflect on communication in a world in which the digital society has disappeared.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Christian Castañeda Noguera, Jordi Resende Moura	Overexploitation, wars, globalization	Short film	video and making-of video	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/un-solo-planeta</u>	Reflect on the fundamental problems that affect our planet.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Daniel Gutiérrez García, Guillermo Sánchez Hernández	Catalonia: history of a nationalism	Research work	pdf document and making-of video	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/la-declaraci%C3%B3n-unilateral</u>	Reflect on the causes of the unilateral declaration of independence of Catalonia.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Mario Dueñas Carbayeda, Alejandro Marcos Campillo, Álvaro	ETA terrorism	website website	website and making-of video	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-</u>	Reflect on the meaning of the terrorist group ETA in the construction of Basque identity and nationalist conflicts in Spain.

	Píríz Sendín				<u>actual/project/terrorismo-eta</u>	
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Teresa Benito Aguilar, Ricardo González Mellado, Elena Martín Sánchez	inclusion of ethnic or religious minorities in our societies	draw	picture and making-of video	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/problemas-identidad-personal</u>	Reflect on the difficulties of inclusion of ethnic or religious minorities in our societies.
IES "Venancio Blanco"	Sergio Sierra Bernal, Cristina Viera Sánchez	War and evolution	draw my life animation	video and making-of video	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/globalizaci%C3%B3n-naci%C3%B3n-e-individuo-mundo-actual/project/guerra-y-evoluci%C3%B3n</u>	Investigate the relations between three wars of the last 100 years, in order to establish relations between them.

Table 3: Oxfam Italia Onlus's artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Universita Roma Tre	Alessio Mirtini	Sociability and social media: help or condemnation?	Online research and news paper article	article		Young people are diminishing face to face interactions in favour of online friendships, which are based on a fake self-representation that helps to become popular and feel accepted, but makes YP feel lonely
Universita Roma Tre	Sarah Penge	Youth and communication: University radio case study"	Qualitative research through interviews	Research project + video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunita-italiana/project/i-giovani-e-la-comunicazione-il-caso-delle-radio-universitarieb	University radios are a very good tool to contrast fake news and develop YP's competences, but in many EU countries they are not recognised and funded.
Universita Roma Tre	Claudia Neroni	Bullying and cyber bullying: how to stem the phenomenon?	Qualitative research through interviews and desk analysis of international influencers	article + video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunita-italiana/project/vittime-di-bullismo-la-storia-di-chi-se-ha-trovato-la-luce	Emotional impact of bullying and cyber bullying on young people. Claudia interviewed a young singer who wrote a song about bullying, analysed a song of Lady Gaga and interviewed by phone the President of the Italian National Centre against Bullying – Bullistop (http://www.bullistop.com/). The president participated also in the showcase workshop organised on the 18th of May 2018 in Rome.
Universita Roma Tre	Maria Chiara Petrassi	Self-representation on social media: comparing two	Qualitative research through	PPT +	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunita-	Self-representation on social media: comparing two generations. What happens to the things that I share on a social? What is "the media narcissism"?

		generations	interviews	video	italiana/project/power-dominion-social-media	And above all, as a result of the scandal Cambridge Analytica, my personal data, are really protected? She did some research and interviewed two people of two different countries and generations. It seems that YP people, who are more familiar with online tools are less aware of the challenging in exposing themselves and their personal data online, while adults are less confident with the technology, but much more aware of the risks in sharing personal data. Media literacy education should be implemented in each school since primary education.
ITT Cristoforo Colombo	Chiara Sanna	What's originate stress in young people?	Qualitative research through interviews	Research report		<p>Usually we think about young people as the happiest and free generation of earth: they don't have particular commitments apart from studying. But, often after school they have sport, extra-curricular activities and for some people even a job.</p> <p>Young people today are pushed to develop more and more competences in order to compete in society with other young people. If we add also the component related to their social condition their lives are even more complicated.</p> <p>For this reason most of young people admit to be stressed, how do they cope with it?</p>
Universita La Sapienza	Simona Ruggiero	How do institutions support schools	Online questionnair	Research report +	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/com	Bullying today takes place mainly on social media but the effects are visible in real life. Students have

		against cyber bullying?	and research report	video	unità-italiana/project/prevention-and-contrast-cyberbullying-and-bullying-how-do	identified a bullied person as someone who introverted, isolated and weak. At national level schools are creating partnerships with the police to train young people about the use of internet and its laws, but young people affirm that schools should have a more direct role in terms of inclusion, support and direct confrontation. Teachers, instead affirm that for them is quite difficult to detect the phenomenon in class.
Universita Rome Tre	Elisabetta Svolacchia	How have the digital era and the economic crisis revolutionised the relationship between youth and labour market?	Qualitative research through interviews and online questionnaires	PPT + video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunita-italiana/project/i-giovani-e-il-mondo-del-lavoro	Tendency of individualism among young people. They consider their own working condition as personal and specific. This allow a naïve positivity that can be a stimulus, but it doesn't allow young people to feel part of a common category. Following this attitude, the survey shows that they are not aware of youth unemployment issue, its dimensions and implications at sociological and political level.
Universita Rome Tre	Gabriele Iannaccone	Citizens' social and electoral participation	Online survey	PPT	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunita-italiana/project/partecipazione-sociale-e-voto	Mathematical analysis of social participation and vote based on a questionnaire. It wanted to show how we vote, the thought of people about old generations, the relationship between social participation and vote, the perception of social involvement and how we can improve it. Findings: the more people perceive as important participating in society, the more they get engaged. It is interesting that among the

						interviewed, the most engaged in society didn't vote for the Italian national elections.
Università La Sapienza	Olga Stelmakhovych, Silvia Fiorucci	How does fear for the employment future influences our present reality?	Qualitative research through interviews	Research project	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunità-italiana/project/la-paura-del-futuro-termini-di-incertezza-lavorativa	<p>The research focuses on young people's perception of future in relation to employment uncertainty. The results of the survey administered to young people from high schools to young workers have raised several reflections:</p> <p>The high unemployment standards scared Italian youth population and with regret everyone dreams to move abroad as soon as possible.</p> <p>Few people know about the meaning of NEET, this means that they are not aware of their condition, therefore they don't advocate for policy change.</p> <p>The interviewed propose to: stimulate hiring, reform third sector, create new didactic programmes with synergies with external world, working experiences controlled by the State, fight against illegal work, reconsider contracts and create programmes to support job research.</p>
Università La Sapienza	Nicoletta D'Antonio, Matteo Cerasoli	Youth and political participation	Qualitative research through interviews	Research project	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunità-italiana/project/giovanità-identità-e-politica-una-storia-alternativa	<p>Following a desk research and the administration of a survey among young people, the final reflections are the following:</p> <p>On a side there is a crisis of participation and care of institution towards young people's needs and ambitions that needs to be analysed through its social and economic aspects. On the other side there is a crisis of young people's concept of</p>

						identity and belonging to a generational group, which finds expression through fine art and other types of participation.
Università Roma Tre	Domenico Fittipaldi	What does democracy mean?	Qualitative research through online survey with open questions	Essay		<p>Among the evidences of the survey: Today's individualism at any cost leads directly or indirectly to political apathy in building our own identities and striving for individual success. Dominant ideology is trying to destroy any precedent collective obligation, starting from sub-cultures through fashion standardisation to the Fordist employment model in decline due to the tertiary model of European economies (but a country cannot live of ICT and tourism).</p>
Università Roma Tre	Noemi Ricci	Globalisation. ONG's denounce and photographic evidence	Qualitative research through online survey with open questions	Article + video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunità-italiana/project/fotografia-che-denuncia	Photographic denounce is a research framed into the macro issues of globalisation and social inequalities. Photography is a tool used by many NGOs to denounce such inequalities. The research aims to find out the level of concern of young people and adults towards this issue with a specific focus on the emotive sphere. The results show that despite the fact young people see a lot of images with detailed attention, they tend not to get very emotional about what they see as they receive too many inputs on a daily basis.
ITT Cristoforo Colombo	Caterina Celi	Integration of young migrants in school	Organisation of social dialogues at school about	Mind map	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunità-italiana/project/una-	The research aims to investigate among schoolmates with migrant background their role as intercultural mediators between the family and the outer society through workshops and theatre.

			integration of 2° generation of migrants in Italy		nuova-generazione-new-generation	
Università Roma Tre	Lorenzo Zoccoli	How is Italy seen by other countries?	Online survey	Article + Video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunità-italiana/project/come-litalia-è-vista-dagli-altri-paesi-how-italy-seen-other	The aim of this research is to understand how Italy and Italians are seen by other Countries; if usual stereotypes - regarding what people throughout the world think about Italian culture - are reliable or not, and what first comes to foreigners' mind when they think about Italy. It seems that Italians are seen always happy and having a good quality of life, but when tourists come to Italy often change their ideas due to all the things that don't work properly.
ITT Cristoforo Colombo	Francesca Pia Perugini	What has changed over the last 10 years, if it has changed, in the perception of people of different cultures?	Qualitative research through interviews	Essay		Due to the wave of racism and stereotypes of the political discourse that affected public opinion perception of people with migratory background, this research investigates inside the family and among friends if and how the perception of immigrants has changed over the last 10 years.

Table 4: PYE Global’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Brighton Pupil Referral Unit	Clare Connelly	Cost of living & housing in Brighton, UK	Images and video of activities, crafts	Video/images	WYRED Platform	<p>Very valuable to learn about the real costs of living, in terms of renting and utility bills, and that such practical information would be helpful for other teens as part of their education</p> <p>Raise of homelessness and how Brighton seemed to have noticeably more people living rough on the streets. Homelessness had doubled in the last year and was second in the country only to London</p> <p>Empathy for those he saw on the streets who couldn’t find affordable housing or were dealing with other issues</p>
DV8 Brighton	Jarlath Rice	Gambling	Video	Video	TBC	<p>Still in the research phase but have made some discoveries about the nature of online gambling.</p> <p>The services offered by the online gambling vendors serve to perpetuate gambling addiction.</p> <p>One young man commented there should be more services available to help people who are</p>

						addicted to gambling and accruing more debts than they can afford and education for young people about the services available to help young people be aware of the dangers and the importance of asking for help and support.
DV8 Brighton	Jarlath Rice	Manual Labourers Video Violence Music Genre Stereotypes Streetwear from Sweatshops Faces of Brighton - How multicultural is your community? 4am in Brighton Young Smokers How does technology affect children?	Video	Video/images	TBC	Discussion on how to frame questions as research projects. Different methods of research available. What would you ask other YP in Europe to respond to your project

					<u>workshops</u>	
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	YP4	Smart filter	Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops	Workshop photos also published on WYRED platform
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	YP5	Dentepate	Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops	Workshop photos also published on WYRED platform. This innovative system looked at the consumption of drinking water while brushing teeth. The solution is a device that optimises the amount of water used and, at the end of the mouth wash, separates waters from other waste products (e.g. toothpaste)
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	YP6	Water cleaning device (WCD)	Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops	Workshop photos also published on WYRED platform
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	YP7	Something cool	Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops	Workshop photos also published on WYRED platform
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	YP8	Everything is better with air	Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/do%C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops	Workshop photos also published on WYRED platform

					<u>C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops</u>	
SOUTH WEST HIGH SCHOOL	YP9	Rain arise	Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%20%20C4%9Fa-community/project/do%20%20C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops	Workshop photos also published on WYRED platform. Recent researches show that households use over 400 litres of water every day of the week. Some innovative technologies can make a big dent in our water usage and our water bills. Smart homes give us insights which help us conserve energy, water, and resources. The idea is to design smart homes to reduce the burden on resources, by using them as efficiently as possible. Reservoirs and pipelines were rebuilt, and systems were designed to pump water to our homes.
HACI RAHIME HIGH SCHOOL	YP10	Master regulator box	Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%20%20C4%9Fa-community/project/do%20%20C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops	Workshop photos also published on WYRED platform
HACI RAHIME HIGH SCHOOL	YP11	Smart Water (SMWR)	Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%20%20C4%9Fa-community/project/do%20%20C4%9Fa-ideation-workshops	Workshop photos also published on WYRED platform
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	EC	MIRACLE SALT: THE ALTERNATIVE S OF NEW	Prototype, project report	Prototype, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%20%20C4%9Fa-community/project/doga	The results of an experiment conducted on a salt called sodium sulphate showed that it dissolves in water and that, when dissolved, it absorbs the heat from the environment and acts

		GENERATION HEAT INSULATION WITH SODIUM SULFATE			<u>-school-projects</u>	<p>as an insulation. This leads to the idea of using sodium sulphate for the insulation of buildings. Globally, there is a great demand increase for energy, due to the increase of the world's population. This need of energy is met with fossil fuel which, however, is already known to have harmful effects for humans and for the environment, not to mention its high cost.</p> <p>Therefore, the use of sodium sulphate to insulate houses can help reduce the need for energy in a sustainable way. Since the salt will be produced locally in a sustainable production cycle, it will support the local economy to supply its own environmentally friendly products.</p>
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	EB	DON'T BE AFRAID KNOW WELL!	Prototype, project report	Prototype, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/doga-community/project/doga-school-projects	<p>This project focuses on the results of the survey about refugees in Turkey. The increase in the refugee population causes feelings of insecurity among citizens. The majority of Turkish citizens have prejudices and stereotypes about refugees. The majority of people prefer to stay away from the refugees, and prefer not to use common areas.</p> <p>As an outcome, it was stated that in order to overcome prejudices, citizens should be trained and well informed about the plight of refugees, so as to foster a peaceful co-living situation.</p>
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	AK and MO	THE POPULATION CHANGE, SOCIAL AND SPATIAL	project report	project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/doga-community/project/doga-school-projects	<p>This study looked at the problems connected to refugees and defectors. It is generally believed that they disturb the community structure in many aspects. At the end of the preliminary interview and workshops about 'minorities and</p>

		EFFECTS AFTER REFUGEE MIGRATIONS IN THE LAST TEN YEARS OF ISTANBUL				respect of differences’, it was shown that perception could be uniquely changed through education. It was determined that stereotypes were changed during the last interview at the end of workshops. The students who received the relevant training in the first focus group, showed off their sensitivity about this subject via posters, banners and leaflets they had prepared during the workshops.
DOGA PRIMARY SCHOOL	BY	THE ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY ROOFS: TO OBTAIN ENERGY FROM RAIN WATER ON THE ROOFS SHAPED IN THE FORM OF M	Prototype, project report	Prototype, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/doga-community/project/doga-school-projects	The use of renewable resources instead of fossil fuel has recently seen an upwards trend. The prototype created by the students aims to obtain energy from the water gathered on roofs, which are designed in the shape of an ‘M’ to collect as much rain as possible, to optimise hydroelectric resources. It was suggested that this energy resource should be disseminated in the regions with high levels of precipitation. Whilst this project can be obtained with an economical cost, regulating the speed of the water flowing from the roof is difficult. Overall, though, since the energy produced can be stored, the usages of this kind of roof should be increased and these stations should be integrated with other renewable energies, such as wind, tidal waves, etc.
DOGA HIGH SCHOOL	YP12	Gender biased idioms, in the past and today	Survey, project report	Survey, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/doga-community/project/doga-school-projects	In the search conducted with the content analysis method, 18 Turkish idioms were detected which contain negative comments about women. It was seen that the status of women in society is perceived to be below men, from an intellectual and social aspect.

						<p>The role of women in society is reduced to being a mother and a house keeper. The concept of equal rights could therefore not be appropriately developed, according to the examined idioms. Attempts should be made to decrease the frequency of occurrence of these fixed idioms that may or may not be used on purpose, but which surely are unhelpful to change society's point of view.</p>
<p>DOGA HIGH SCHOOL</p>	<p>DO and EA</p>	<p>Zero waste with Chlorella vulgaris</p>	<p>Prototype; project report</p>	<p>Prototype; project report</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%20-%20community/project/doga-school-projects</p>	<p>The findings of the research show that chlorella vulgaris can absorb carbon dioxide. In this project, chlorella vulgaris was used in factory chimneys to lower the water footprint, since it filters without leaving any biological waste. It also produces an alternative compost, which is completely environment friendly. The ultimate aim is to create a remedy against global warming.</p>

Table 6: Early Years – The organisation for young children LBG

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
	YP1	Why do children tell lies on the Internet?	Data Collection Analysis	Report; images; work products; video; posters	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/why-do-children-tell-lies-internet/project/why-do-children-tell-lies-internet	The links contains numerous artefacts produced by children working on the topic

Table 7: Youth for exchange and understanding international AISBL’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
	Cristiano Altamura	The relationship between digital identity and stress in young people - Does Digital Identity (life in SM) lead to stressful behaviour in real life?	N/A	N/A	N/A	No comments available yet
	Simone Salvati	Which level is better to cover employment prospects	Survey	Survey	N/A	comparing local to international level on the topic of employment prospects, participants believe that the link between local and international is the solution; There is a huge necessity to change education systems, however the issue of linkage to technology gathers the least “support”; Majority of young people who took part, see themselves migrating for working purposes.
	Stefano Gandini	The use of Digital as content in Education.	Survey	Survey	N/A	Promote and raise awareness within stakeholders on the fact that education cannot be separated from technology, as it plays an increasingly preponderant role in today's reality; Promote the introduction of digital tools into education, as it can optimize learning time, provide greater teaching support and improve quality; Need to link education to technological innovations. Doing so and granting access to

						<p>these technologies can shape new habits and new types of learning;</p> <p>Also, linking education to the digital innovations can lead to the development of different approaches locally and globally.</p>
	Giulia Muzzurru	Are young people aware of privacy and safety aspect when being online?	Survey	Survey	N/A	<p>The majority of young people think that internet, today, is very useful because makes easy our modern lifestyle. They think also that all types of excess can be a danger so excessive use of internet could be dangerous and it can make you a "social addicted". If internet is used in the right way it could bring only advantages. For sure internet has an impact on our behavior and social interactions</p>
	Murat Mislimi	“What is the impact of Social Media on building awareness and understanding around gender and gender identities?”	N/A	N/A	N/A	<p>To a small extend there are some sources that do promote understanding and awareness;</p> <p>There are a lot of aggressive and “hate” related messages online;</p> <p>There is the need to promote a gender sensitive educational approach online and offline from early years;</p> <p>Link Formal Education and Non-Formal Education to promote online sources on education, support and awareness on the matter of gender and gender identities.</p>
	Giulia Annibaletti / Silvana Muratori	"Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions through the eyes of children: how are differences perceived?"	N/A	N/A	N/A	No conclusions yet

		"Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions: cultural development - can the virtual/digital tools help? how?"			https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tolerance-towards-different-culturesopinions/forum/subgroup-b-group-working-cultural	<p>Focus on multilingual approaches and learning;</p> <p>Promote the value of diversity, understood as cultural and human enrichment, that can lead to the concept of integration;</p> <p>Foster initiatives and commit to the promotion of inclusive ecosystems in education and venues (e.g. Libraries), while offering a dialogue with local administrations;</p> <p>Promote the use of virtual spaces and digital tools as they indeed help (digital books, online courses, technological tools in education etc).</p>
		"Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions from an intergenerational perspective: online generation vs. offline generation"				No recommendations yet
		"Tolerance towards different cultures and opinions at school - what's the perception of migrant students and how does the virtual world affect reality on this topic?"	Questionnaire	Questionnaire	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tolerance-towards-different-culturesopinions/forum/subgroup-d-group-working-youth	<p>The research tackles the perception of young Italian and foreign students on the subject of tolerance towards opinions and cultures which are “different from theirs.” How is diversity in the classroom and in the non-school environment? How is the theme dealt within the family? What do they learn from the media?</p> <p>Objective: To investigate the perception and opinion of middle school children about the issues of tolerance and discrimination by referring to their personal experience</p>

Table 8: Moves's artefacts list

Organisation	Project Leads	Research Questions	Artefacts	Comments and Conclusions
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			Type	Format	Link	
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	janrosenberger Stefan_Mann2017 Francesco Trivisonne	Renewable Energies	Scientific text	Appeal to the European Parliament (for use at the European Youth Event)	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/renewable-energies-alternatives/project/appeal-european-parliament	Importance of renewable energies for the future world. Specifically they talk about hydropower and solar-energy. They provide Chinese examples ("Donghai Bridge Wind Farm" or "Panda Power Plant") for combating climate change and invite the European Union to see the perspective of enhancing environmentally sustainable energy resources. They provide a suggestion how to make agricultural areas available for wind turbines, high altitude wind power and solar power by assuring with a legal act, that every member state will provide a certain percentage of the agricultural area in order to generate green power.

<p>Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen</p>	<p>Valentina Borowansky</p>	<p>Prison School - "Gefängnis Schule"</p>	<p>Introspection</p>	<p>Scientific essay</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-austria/project/prison-school-gef%C3%A4ngnis-schule</p>	<p>There are already several dynamic teachers applying innovative approaches in didactics and methodology. However, this is just one side of the step. The other side is the system itself which, in the way described above, involves parents, teachers and young people. A further important step is constituted by democratic, alternative school forms like, for example, “Kapriole in Freiburg”, “The free school in Leipzig”, which focus on children's and young people's´ individual resources while teachers act as empowering “coaches for learning”, also focusing on peer-learning and on instilling curiosity in the learners. Maybe this is not the ultimate solution for our old system, but it moves in the right direction. We need to start learning, understanding, exploring and researching again. The people of tomorrow need a school of tomorrow.</p>
<p>Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen</p>	<p>Neumannbianca lisa.birett Ali-gator</p>	<p>Modern Technologies - and their Effects on Tourism Industry</p>	<p>Literature research</p>	<p>Scientific text</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/new-technologies-tourism/projec</p>	<p>Analysis of the new technologies (list), which are relevant for the tourism industry. The research identifies three forms of modern technology impacting the tourism industry: Virtual Reality, Algorithms, and Robotics and briefly</p>

					t/modern-technologies-and-their-effects-tourism-industry	explain their effects.
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	zasch	Effects of Industry 4.0 on Tourism Industry - Development from E-Tourism to M-Tourism	Literature research	Scientific text	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/new-technologies-tourism/project/effects-industry-40-tourism-industry-development	Research based on the idea from E-Tourism to M-Tourism. Based on recent tendencies, online travel agencies will be more likely to be used instead of travel agencies. Which does not necessarily mean that travel agencies will completely fade from the market.
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	Marina.Ramani maschnina franziska_skolnik	Modern Slavery	Literature research	Scientific text	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-austria/project/modern-slavery	Illustration of the disastrous working-conditions of foreign-workers in Dubai, being one of the column for the enormous per capita income of the inhabitants.

Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	elsabogner chiara.ebner	Trade Agreements within the European Union	Literature research	Scientific text	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/economy-and-trade-eu/project/trade-agreements-within-european-union	The research shows the impacts of the CETA agreement between the EU and Canada on different levels and understand by this why these agreements are of high importance to the future economy, which means to YP. The authors invite to discuss about the topic..
Produktionsschule Eggenburg	Sedetka	Sedetka - this is my life	Introspection	Texts, poems, statements, reflections	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-%C3%B6sterreich/project/sedetka-my-life	Reflections on life from a teenager (texts, reflections, statements, poems)
Produktionsschule Eggenburg	derkoffer1 Zeref36 T78 Tyfoon	Gaming - I love it!	Discussion and exchange	Thread on Platform	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-%C3%B6sterreich/project/gaming-i-love-	Fascination on gaming has for them in presenting the voices of rappers. It turns out that this has a lot to do with being a valuable part of a community. A member of a community who is appreciated and who's contribution to the game is regarded as a being welcomed and wanted

					it	
Produktionsschule Eggenburg	ParaxLivestream T78	Mobbing	Introspection	Collage	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-%C3%B6sterreich/project/mobbing	Thoughts and a call from young people regarding mobbing in their environments
Produktionsschule Eggenburg	Jesse JackyNovak T78	Environmental pollution	Creative work	Handicraft	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-%C3%B6sterreich/project/environmental-pollution	Reminder and showing the dangers of nuclear power plants

Produktions- schule Eggenburg	BlackiPai Shadow	Future professions	Creative WorK	Painting	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-%C3%B6sterreich/project/our-future-professions	Young teenagers express their feeling about their future employments
Produktions- schule Eggenburg	Vasile76	Don't give up!	Sharing of Reflections	Text-Statement	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/das-ist-die-eggenburg-gruppe-aus-%C3%B6sterreich/project/dont-give	Considerations and thoughts from a teenager about following its aims and dreams and encourage other to follow their dreams and try to achieve them

Table 9: Boundaries observatory C.I.C’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Unaffiliated	Robyn Watkins-Davies, Flo Cross, Asher Courts, Edie Bainbridge, Rebecca Dion, Leila Sweeney, Gabe Owens,	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	Presentation - a vision for yoga in schools	Powerpoint document	Pending upload	<p>Reflexion and research process on how yoga helps YP. They carried out a survey of attitudes to yoga in one of the participants schools. They created a blueprint for yoga in education which they presented to 110 people at a yoga and education conference in London, a shared vision of what how yoga could be incorporated into the curriculum.</p> <p>As a result of this, the coordinator of team was invited to participate in the UK All Party Parliamentary Group on Yoga in education, healthcare, the workplace and prisons, which os working on how to incorporate yoga into policy in these areas. It is important that the voice of the young is being heard at these levels of policy and that they are part of the conversation. The notion of the digital society was very much in the background. When asked they recognized the influence of social media, for example, on their lives and stress</p>

						levels, but saw it as simply part of the context, as opposed to an issue in itself.
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Unaffiliated	Robyn Watkins-Davies	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	My personal development through yoga	Audio file	Pending upload	
Unaffiliated	Flo Cross,	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	My personal development through yoga	Audio file	Pending upload	
Unaffiliated	Asher Courts,	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	My personal development through yoga	Audio file	Pending upload	
Unaffiliated	Edie Bainbridge	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	My personal development through yoga	Audio file	Pending upload	
Unaffiliated	Rebecca Dion	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	My personal development through yoga	Audio file	Pending upload	
Unaffiliated	Leila Sweeney	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	My personal development through yoga	Audio file	Pending upload	
Unaffiliated	Gabe Owens,	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	My personal development through yoga	Audio file	Pending upload	
Unaffiliated	Robyn Watkins-Davies, Flo Cross, Asher Courts,	How can yoga help young people in the digital age?	Our development through yoga	Prezi file	Pending link	

	Edie Bainbridge, Rebecca Dion, Leila Sweeney, Gabe Owens,					
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Table 10: Tel Aviv University’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
“Hof HaSharon” regional high school.	Valy Shtainhart (teacher)	What’s wrong with the education system and how it can be improved.	Summary of discussions 2. Drawing/Painting	Word Doc Graffiti (to be completed)		<p>Decision makers in the education system should listen to young persons and understand them in order to alleviate the burden that students experience. They should come not just to hear us but also to really listen.</p> <p>Changing the education approach and the curriculum. Reducing the workload and more consideration of students' private lives.</p> <p>To open the possibility for students to choose the topics of learning, namely allowing them to choose the subjects of study in a broader manner.</p> <p>Reduce the number of compulsory subjects.</p> <p>Changing the reform done in the high school curriculum, returning the start of matriculation exams to 10-th grade, and distributing the exams over the three years in high school.</p> <p>The implementation of so-called “meaningful learning” in a clearer and broader sense.</p>

						<p>To stop causing the students to just “throw up” the learned material, with an emphasis on changing the teacher-student relationship.</p> <p>Especially to emphasize the significant reduction of pressure on high school students and the expansion of their activity possibilities after the school hours.</p>
School of Transformative Media	YP1	How film-making could help students with special needs to cope with their problems	Short film?	Video		Preliminary preparations started. No comments available yet

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